

SPATIAL JUSTICE AOTEAROA

(Re)designing Māori Streets: Priorities and Pathways for Supporting Urban Aotearoa Street Design – White Paper

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Executive Summary

Street design in Aotearoa has profound implications for wellbeing, identity, and equity. Street environments, however, have largely been shaped by planning frameworks that marginalise Māori authority, cultural presence, and relationships to whenua and te taiao. This White Paper addresses that gap by outlining why Māori street design matters, what Māori communities prioritise, and how Māori-led street design can be realised in practice.

The paper synthesises three sources of evidence: a targeted review of Māori-relevant literature, a national Māori Streets Survey, and Māori-led design wānanga. Together, these sources show that Māori street design is not only about physical form, but about restoring relationships between people and place. Māori community members consistently prioritised safety, walkability, visible Māori identity, access to nature, and meaningful Māori involvement in decision-making. Through the wānanga, these priorities were deepened into coherent Māori-led design principles and shared visions for future streets.

From this synthesis, the paper identifies a set of priority outcomes that Māori street environments are expected to deliver. While aspirational, these outcomes are grounded in lived experience and provide clear direction for incremental change, pilot projects, and long-term transformation. Although centred on Māori worldviews and leadership, the outcomes consistently support inclusive and equitable environments for all who live in and move through these places.

The paper outlines pathways for change across systems and governance, design and planning, and implementation and delivery. It concludes with a focused set of recommendations to support Māori leadership, capability, and partnership in street design, and to align investment and evaluation with wellbeing, cultural vitality, and environmental resilience.

Priority Outcomes for Māori Street Design

Restored relationships with whenua and te taiao

Streets that support ecological health, climate resilience, and Māori responsibilities as kaitiaki.

Wellbeing across generations

Street environments that support walking, rest, play, and social connection for tamariki, pakeke, and kaumātua.

Visible Māori identity and belonging

Streets that normalise Māori presence through naming, storytelling, materials, and design connected to whakapapa and place.

Safe, people-centred movement

Streets where walking and wheeling feel safe and supported, with reduced dominance of vehicles.

Stronger whānau and community connection

Streets that function as shared spaces for gathering, interaction, and collective life.

Meaningful Māori leadership and partnership

Streets created and developed through shared or Māori-led decision-making, not consultation alone.

This White Paper can be used to:

- Guide street design and planning processes that centre Māori aspirations
- Inform policy, funding, and investment decisions
- Support co-design partnerships with mana whenua and Māori communities
- Assess whether street environments are delivering cultural, social, and environmental outcomes
- Reframe streets as sites of cultural presence, care, and power, not just movement.

Introduction

Streets shape how people move, connect and participate in everyday life. Māori wellbeing is interconnected with relationships to whenua and the natural environment, yet these relationships are rarely reflected in contemporary street environments. Urban planning in Aotearoa has historically been informed by colonial frameworks that imposed standardised street forms and governance systems, limiting Māori authority, cultural expression, and ecological integration in urban environments.

Indigenous planning scholarship has shown how colonial-era planning continues to marginalise Māori perspectives and presence in the built environment (Jojola, 2008; Matunga, 2013). Māori wellbeing research indicates that cultural identity, ecological connection, and community cohesion are supported when Māori values are reflected in the places where people live and move (Boulton et al., 2021). These bodies of work underscore the need for street design approaches that centre Māori worldviews and support healthy, inclusive, connected and culturally grounded communities.

This White paper responds to that need by bringing together Māori-relevant literature, a national Māori Streets Survey, and Māori-led design wānanga to set out a coherent, Māori-led approach to redesigning streets in Aotearoa. It is intended for policymakers, planners, designers, mana whenua and Māori communities working to reframe street environments that better reflect Māori realities and aspirations and support long-term wellbeing.

The work presented in this White Paper draws on a staged research process. A targeted scoping review was first undertaken to identify gaps in current street planning practice and to direct the development of a national Māori Streets Survey. The survey translated these issues into community-facing questions, identifying shared priorities and areas of concern. Survey participants were then invited to take part in a series of online design wānanga, where preliminary survey findings were used as prompts to support collective reflection and design thinking. Insights from the wānanga form the foundation of the Māori street design principles, priority outcomes, and pathways presented in this paper.

Detailed findings from the Māori Streets Survey and the Design Wānanga are documented in accompanying project reports.

Why Māori Street Design Matters

Despite increasing attention to liveability, safety, and sustainability in urban design, street planning in Aotearoa remains largely influenced by structural assumptions that limit its relevance to Māori community members. Streets are typically conceived as technical infrastructures, governed through standardised design codes and performance measures that prioritise efficiency, uniformity and control. These approaches leave little room for Māori values, relationships to place, or community-defined aspirations to meaningfully guide streetscape environments.

A central issue identified in the literature is the ongoing marginalisation of Māori authority in planning and designing processes. Colonial governance frameworks embedded in urban planning have historically positioned Māori as stakeholders or users rather than as decision-makers with rights, responsibilities, and whakapapa relationships to the whenua. As a result,

street environments are rarely directed by Māori-led processes or grounded in local knowledge of mana whenua, reinforcing patterns of cultural absence and limited recognition of Māori presence in public space.

The literature also highlights a broader misalignment between dominant planning logics and Māori ways of living and relating to place. Standardised street forms often reflect individualised, movement-focused assumptions that sit uneasily alongside Māori values centred on relationality, collectivity, and connection to te taiao. Where streets prioritise circulation over gathering, and regulation over everyday use, they can constrain social connection, cultural expression, and intergenerational interaction.

Taken together, these structural conditions help explain why contemporary street environments frequently fail to support Māori wellbeing, identity, and environmental relationships. They also underscore the need to rethink how streets are conceived, governed, and designed, starting from Māori worldviews rather than retrofitting cultural elements into existing planning frameworks.

Understanding these structural conditionals provides important context for how Māori community members experience, access, and prioritise change with street environments today.

Insights from the Māori Streets Survey

The Māori Streets Survey provides insights into what Māori community members prioritise when asked to reflect on existing street environments and imagine what a better Māori street could be. Survey findings combine ranked feature preferences with written comments, offering both a sense of scale and insight into how participants described their experiences and aspirations. Across responses, participants consistently highlighted the importance of safety, access, cultural presence, environmental care, and Māori participation in decision-making. These priorities were evident both in the features most frequently rated as “must-haves” and in the language participants used to describe what makes a street usable, welcoming, or limiting.

How streets function: movement, access and use

Survey results showed strong support for features that enable safe and accessible movement. Pedestrian-friendly walking paths, well-maintained and accessible streets, adequate lighting, and reliable public transport were among the highest-rated “must-have” features. These priorities were reinforced by comments describing difficulties navigating footpaths, crossing roads, and streets that do not accommodate prams, wheelchairs, or people with limited mobility. Participants also linked movement to practical considerations such as seating, shelter, and proximity to services. Comments frequently noted that without these features, walking longer distances or using streets comfortably was difficult or avoided altogether.

How streets feel: safety, comfort and belonging

The *feel* or atmosphere of the street emerged as a distinct and important concern. Many participants rated a safe and calm street environment as essential and used their comments to describe how feelings of comfort, exposure, or unease influenced how they used their street. Traffic speed, noise, lighting, and the presence or absence of people were commonly referenced as shaping whether a street felt welcoming or avoided. Several participants described the street in relational terms, linking atmosphere to care, connection, and the

presence of others. Streets that felt supportive were associated with a sense of belonging, while streets that felt hostile or unsafe were described as discouraging movement and social interaction.

How streets look: cultural presence, nature, and care

Cultural identity and environmental features were consistently prioritised across the survey. Māori culture and identity features ranked highly overall, with participants emphasising Māori naming, signage, artworks, and design elements that reflect whakapapa and local narratives. These preferences were echoed in comments describing frustration with streets that feel generic or disconnected from Māori and mana whenua identity.

Environmental features were also strongly supported, particularly native planting, trees, and stormwater management. Participants frequently associated greener streets with wellbeing, shade, and respect for whenua and wai, indicating that visual expressions of care for place were important makers of a good (Māori) street environment.

Power, participation and Māori (street) control

In addition to physical features, the survey revealed clear preferences about decision-making. Most participants supported shared decision-making between Māori and other groups across all street features. In contrast, strong support for full Māori control was expressed for Māori culture and identity (street) elements in particular. Very few respondents felt Māori input was not required in street features. Written responses reinforced these findings, with participants expressing frustration with consultations imposed by power dynamics and a desire for meaningful Māori involvement in shaping street outcomes. These responses indicate that questions of power and participation are integral to how Māori assess street environments.

These survey findings illustrate shared priorities across a wide group of Māori community members, while also highlighting the limits of survey data alone in capturing how Māori-led street design might be realised in practice.

Wānanga Findings: Design Principles for Māori Streets

The design wānanga provided space for Māori community members to collectively explore what Māori-led street design could look, feel, and function like in practice. Many participants had also completed the Māori Streets Survey, allowing the wānanga to build directly on previously identified priorities and to deepen them through kōrero, shared reflections, and creative expression.

Across six online wānanga, participants articulated a remarkably consistent vision of Māori streets. While individual drawings and discussions reflected local contexts and personal preferences, the ideas shared repeatedly converged around a small set of core values, spatial logics, and design intentions. These shared directions underpinned the Māori street design principles and priority outcomes presented in this paper.

Strong continuity between survey priorities and wānanga visions

The wānanga confirmed and extended the priorities identified in the survey. Themes such as safety, walking, cultural visibility, access to nature, shared spaces, and Māori participation in

decision-making reappeared throughout participants' drawings and kōrero. Rather than introducing new or competing priorities, the wānanga revealed how these concerns are interconnected and how they might be expressed spatially.

Participants moved beyond listing or rating features to describing relationships between people and whenua, housing and movement, culture and daily life. This shift from prioritisation to interpretation marks a key distinction between the survey and the wānanga: the survey identified *what* matters, while the wānanga explored *how* those priorities come together in place.

Core patterns shaping Māori street design

Analysis of the wānanga kōrero and drawings revealed several recurring patterns that were reflected in participants' visions of Māori streets. Streets were consistently described as ecological and relational environments rather than transport corridors. Te taiao was positioned as the organising foundation, with streets imagined as following landforms, water systems, and seasonal rhythms, supported by native (indigenous) planting, blue-green infrastructure, and sensory connection to nature.

Communal and intergenerational life was another dominant pattern. Participants repeatedly described streets as places for gathering, sharing kai, learning, play, and everyday interaction. These social functions were closely linked to housing arrangements inspired by papakāinga principles, enabling proximity, care, and collective wellbeing across generations.

Movement was also reimagined through a people-first lens. Rather than prioritising speed or efficiency, participants emphasised slow, safe environments that supported walking and wheeling, particularly for tamariki and kaumātua. Curved street layouts, reduced vehicle dominance, and pathways aligned with whenua were common expressions of this intent.

Cultural identity was expected to be visible and normalised throughout the street environment. Participants described Māori naming, narratives, artwork, materials, and spatial cues as integral to street form, expressing whakapapa and mana whenua presence as part of daily life rather than as symbolic additions.

Māori values underpinning design principles

Underlying these spatial patterns were clear Te Ao Māori values. Whanaungatanga, kaitiakitanga, manaakitanga, rangatiratanga, and mātauranga Māori were repeatedly evident in participants' kōrero and framed how they described the purpose and character of Māori streets. These values underpinned both the cultural intentions and the practical design directions identified through the wānanga.

The resulting Māori street design principles translate these values into guidance for how streets can be experienced, as places that support wellbeing, ecological care, cultural expression, and collective life. They form the foundation for the priority outcomes and pathways for action that follow. These wānanga findings shift the discussion from priorities and preferences to a coherent Māori-led vision of street design, providing a basis for identifying the outcomes Māori street environments are expected to deliver.

Priority Outcomes for Māori Street Design

The wānanga findings indicate that Māori-led street design is not only about physical form, but about the outcomes streets are expected to deliver for people, place, and future generations. Drawing from shared priorities identified in the survey and deepened through collective design kōrero, this section outlines the key outcomes Māori street environments are expected to support.

Viewed collectively, the outcomes reflect both Māori values and practical expectations for how streets function as lived spaces. They provide a clear basis for assessing success and for guiding future design, investment, and governance decisions.

Streets that restore relationships with whenua and te taiao

Māori streets are expected to strengthen relationships with land, water, and the natural environment. This includes restoring ecological systems, supporting indigenous biodiversity, and designing with natural landforms and water flows rather than overriding them. Streets that reflect care for the whenua and wai contribute to environmental resilience and reinforce Māori responsibilities as kaitiaki.

Streets that support wellbeing across generations

Participants consistently described streets as spaces that affect physical, social, and cultural wellbeing. Priority outcomes include environments that support walking, rest, play, and social connection for tamariki, pakeke, and kaumātua alike. Streets are expected to enable intergenerational presence and everyday interactions, contributing to healthier, more connected neighbourhood life.

Streets that express Māori identity and belonging

Māori street environments are expected to reflect identity, whakapapa, and local narratives visibly. This includes normalising Māori presences through naming, storytelling, materials, and design cues embedded throughout the street. Streets that express identity foster a sense of belonging and recognition, reinforcing that Māori culture is part of the everyday urban landscape.

Streets that enable safe, people-centred movement

Safety emerged as a foundational outcome across the research. Māori streets are expected to support movement that prioritises people over vehicles, creating environments where walking and wheeling feel safe, comfortable, and supported. Slower movement, clear sightlines, and reduced traffic dominance contribute to streets that people choose to use and spend time in.

Streets that strengthen whānau and community connection

Streets are expected to function as shared spaces that support social interaction, collective activity, and whānau life. Priority outcomes include environments that encourage gathering, shared use, and informal connection, rather than isolating people within private or vehicle-dominated spaces. These outcomes reinforce streets as social infrastructure, not just transport corridors.

Streets governed through Māori participation and leadership

Beyond physical outcomes, Māori street design is expected to support meaningful Māori involvement in decision-making. This includes shared governance arrangements and, where appropriate, Māori-led control over cultural and design outcomes. Streets that reflect Māori values are inseparable from the processes through which they are planned, delivered and maintained.

This set of priority outcomes clarifies what Māori street design is intended to achieve and forms the foundation for the pathways and actions outlined in the following section.

Pathways for Change

Achieving Māori-led street design outcomes requires coordinated shifts across systems, design practice, and delivery processes. The pathways outlined below translate the priorities and outcomes identified through the literature, survey, and wānanga into practical directions for action. Rather than prescribing a single model, these pathways highlight where changes are needed and how Māori values and leadership can be meaningfully embedded.

System and governance pathways

Structural change is essential to enable Māori-led street design. Current planning and investment systems often limit Māori authority and constrain the ability to realise culturally grounded outcomes. Key governance pathways include embedding Te Ao Māori within planning frameworks and decision-making processes, recognising Māori as partners rather than consultees.

Resourcing is a critical enabler. Māori organisations, iwi, hapū, and community groups require sustained funding and institutional support to participate meaningfully and to lead where appropriate. Long-term investment approaches that prioritise wellbeing, cultural vitality, and environmental care, rather than short-term efficiency, are necessary to support enduring outcomes.

Clear accountability mechanisms are also needed to ensure that Māori involvement is embedded in decisions and outcomes, not just processes. Shared governance arrangements, transparent roles, and agreed measures of success can help build trust and legitimacy over time.

Design and planning pathways

Design pathways focus on shifting how streets are conceived and framed. Māori street design requires moving beyond standardised templates toward place-responsive approaches rooted in whenua, wai, and local narratives. This includes adopting Māori street frameworks that integrate cultural, environmental, and social considerations from the outset.

Design processes should prioritise people-first movement, communal spaces, and intergenerational use, while visibly expressing Māori identity through naming, storytelling,

materials, and form. Taiao-led design, incorporating indigenous planting, climate-responsive features, and ecological restoration, should be treated as foundational rather than supplementary.

Importantly, design pathways must remain flexible. Māori street design is not a fixed aesthetic, but a set of values and relationships that must be interpreted differently across contexts.

Implementation and delivery pathways

Implementation pathways focus on how Māori street design is delivered in practice. Pilot projects developed in partnership with mana whenua provide opportunities to test approaches, build confidence, and demonstrate outcomes. These pilots should be treated as learning environments, supported by adaptive and iterative processes rather than rigid delivery models.

Community activation is also essential. Streets designed to support gathering, walking, and shared use rely on ongoing care, programming, and everyday presence. Supporting local stewardships and use helps ensure that physical changes translate into lived outcomes.

Climate resilience should be integrated at all stages of delivery, from planning through to maintenance. Streets that respond to heat, flooding, and environmental change contribute to long-term community resilience while reinforcing Māori responsibilities as kaitiaki.

Māori-led street design outcomes can be realised through aligned governance, design, and delivery approaches that support long-term wellbeing, cultural vitality, and environmental resilience.

Recommendations

To support Māori-led street design in practice, this White Paper makes the following recommendations for government agencies, local authorities, mana whenua, and delivery partners.

Establish Māori-led governance for street design

Government and local authorities should formalise shared or Māori-led governance arrangements for street projects, particularly where mana whenua have a strong presence. This includes clear decision-making roles, accountability mechanisms, and authority over cultural and design outcomes.

Fund Māori capability and leadership as core infrastructure

Dedicated, long-term funding should be provided to Māori organisations and collectives to lead, partner in, and steward street design initiatives. Māori participation should be resourced as essential infrastructure, not treated as an add-on to delivery, with targeted support to build design, technical, and governance capability within mana whenua and Māori organisations.

Pilot Māori street design approaches in diverse contexts

Agencies should invest in a small number of Māori street pilot projects developed in partnership with mana whenua. These pilots should test Māori-led design principles, support learning across sectors, and build confidence in alternative street models.

Shift street design practice toward place- and taiao-led approaches

Planning and design guidance should be revised to support streets guided by whenua, wai, and local narratives, prioritising walking, shared use, and ecological function over standardised, vehicle-dominated templates.

Measure success through wellbeing, culture and resilience

Evaluation frameworks should move beyond traffic performance metrics and assess street projects against Māori-defined outcomes, including wellbeing, cultural presence and vitality, environmental health, and community use.

The recommendations provide a focused set of actions to operationalise the pathways for change outlined in this paper and to support Māori-led street design in Aotearoa.

Conclusion

This White Paper has brought together Māori-relevant literature, a national survey, and Māori-led design wānanga results to clarify why Māori street design matters and how it can be realised in practice. Across all stages of the research, a consistent message emerged: current street environments are structurally misaligned with Māori values, authority, and ways of relating to place, yet Māori community members hold clear and shared aspirations for streets that better support wellbeing, identity, and environmental care.

Survey and wānanga participants consistently emphasised the importance of streets that visibly reflect Māori identity in everyday life. These expectations were not framed as symbolic additions, but as integral to how streets are experienced, used, and valued. In this sense, Māori street design speaks to the cultural foundations of Aotearoa and to the role of public spaces in expressing them.

The design principles and outcomes articulated through the wānanga were intentionally aspirational. They challenge inherited planning norms and expand what is considered possible with street design, while remaining grounded in lived experience and collective responsibility. Rather than representing fixed end-states, these visions provide direction for incremental change, pilot projects, and longer-term transformation.

This paper also recognises the limits of street design alone. Māori street design cannot resolve entrenched inequities associated with housing, income, or health in isolation. However, when aligned with broader structural changes, streets can contribute meaningfully to physical activity, social connection, cultural presence, and environmental resilience, particularly in communities experiencing long-standing disadvantage.

Although centred on Māori worldviews and leadership, the outcomes identified through his work consistently support inclusive and equitable environments for all who live in and move through

these places. Through Māori leadership, partnership, and sustained commitment, streets can become spaces that restore relationships between people and place – and contribute to a more just and resilient Aotearoa.

Mauri Ora

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